

Microwave-irradiated synthesis and biological evaluation of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines as antibacterial and anti-inflammatory agents

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In a wide search program towards a biologically active antibacterial and anti-inflammatory agents, a series of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline have been synthesized with excellent yields employing microwave techniques starting from substituted α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds which undergo cyclization reactions with phenylhydrazine. The structures of newly synthesized compounds were characterized and confirmed on the basis of FT-IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral analyses. The synthesized compounds 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines had shown significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 87), *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 40), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 424) and *Proteus vulgaris* (MTCC 426) by cup plate method using tetracycline-SD 037 as a reference standard. The anti-inflammatory property of 1,3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines were screened by using carragenan induced paw edema method in Wistar rat. The anti-inflammatory activities were comparable to that of the standard drug diclofenac. The safety of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines were reflected by toxicity studies.

Keywords: Chalcones, pyrazolines, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, analgesic.

Introduction

Considerable interest has been focused on the pyrazoline structures, some of which are known to be biologically active and important constituents of many pharmaceutical¹ and agrochemical products². As an important class of biologically active agent pyrazoline possesses a broad spectrum of biological activities such as antibacterial³, antifungal⁴, anti-depressant⁵, antidiabetic⁶, antiacetylcholinesterase⁷, anti-inflammatory, analgesic⁸, antiangiogenic and antioxidant⁹. 2-Pyrazoline being important nitrogen containing five containing heterocyclic compounds is most frequently studied heterocyclic compounds. With this background, it is considered worthwhile to synthesize 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines¹⁰ starting from simple condensation of substituted acetophenones with variously substituted aldehydes to give α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds (**2a-j**) and a subsequent cyclization reaction with phenylhydrazines to **3a-j**. It is also important to screen them for antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities. The chalcones possessing α,β -

unsaturated ketone group, when reacted with phenylhydrazine underwent condensation and subsequent ring closure to give 2-pyrazolines (**3a-j**).

The involvement of carbonyl group (C=O) in the reaction was indicated by the absence of absorption band at 1658 cm⁻¹ and presence of a characteristic absorption band at 1597 cm⁻¹ due to (C=N) stretching frequency of pyrazoline in the IR spectra of **3a**. Similarly chemical shift in ¹³C NMR reflected at δ 190.63 due to (C=O) group of **2a**, which was absent in corresponding 2-pyrazoline rather represented at δ 135.57 due to (C=N).

The ¹H NMR spectrum of **3a-j** exhibited two doublets of doublets at δ 2.98–3.17, 3.79–3.95 and 5.20–5.67 due to Ha, Hb of (-CH₂) and Hc of (-CH-) proton of 2-pyrazoline respectively. Multiplets were appeared due to aromatic protons with the expected chemical shift and integral value.

The mass spectrum of **2a** was recorded as additional evidence to the proposed structure. It exhibited molecular ion peak at *m/z* 208 corresponding to its molecular weight.

The other predominant peaks, which were appeared at m/z 178, 105, 89, 77 and 51 were in consistent with expected fragmentation pattern. The mass spectrum of **3a** was recorded at m/z 298 corresponding to its molecular weight. The other predominant peaks, which were appeared at m/z 220, 180, 105 and 63 were in consistent with expected fragmentation patterns.

In present study an attempt has been made to find out the efficiency of inhibition of bacterial growth in Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Proteus vulgaris*, and inflammation in Wister Albino rat.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR affinity series-I using KBr and ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Avance II 400 NMR spectrometer using CDCl_3 as solvent and TMS as an internal standard and peak values are shown in δ ppm. Mass spectra were recorded on AGILENT gas chromatography-mass spectrometer. The purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel plates.

General procedure for the preparation of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines (3a-j) using microwave-irradiation method:

The appropriate mixture of 1,3-diaryl prop-2-ene-1-one (0.1 mol), phenyl hydrazine (0.1 mol) and glacial acetic acid (20 mL) was subjected to microwave irradiation at 210 W, for 10–15 min to afford 2-pyrazolines. The reaction was monitored for completion using TLC. The product obtained was filtered and washed with warm methanol in order to remove adhered acetic acid and recrystallized from ethanol to get pure compounds.

Methods:

Antibacterial activity:

The synthesized compounds were screened for *in vitro* antibacterial activity¹¹ against Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 87) and Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 40), *Proteus vulgaris* (MTCC 426) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 424) by cup-plate method¹² at a concentration 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in DMSO solution using tetracycline-SD 037 as a reference standard. Mueller-Hinton broth was used as medium for antibacterial activity. The Petri dishes were incubated at 36°C for 24 h. Inhibition was recorded by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone at the end of the 24 h. Each experiment was repeated

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines (**3a-j**).

Compounds	x	y
3a	H	H
3b	<i>p</i> -Cl	H
3c	<i>p</i> -Br	H
3d	H	<i>m,p</i> -OCH ₃
3e	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -Cl
3f	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
3g	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl
3h	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m,p</i> -OCH ₃
3i	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
3j	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -Br

duplicate and average of the two independent determinations was recorded. All the 2-pyrazoline compounds showed significant activity against these organisms.

Animals:

Wistar Albino rats (150–200 g) of either sex were used. The animals housed under standard laboratory conditions maintained at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and under 12/12 h light/dark cycle and fed with standard pellet diet (Gold Mohur brand, Lipton India Limited.) and water *ad libitum*. The experimental protocols were approved by Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (Regn No: 926/ab/06/CPSEEA).

Acute toxicity study:

Acute toxicity of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline derivatives were determined in Albino Wistar rats with the staircase method³. Each group of 6 animals was fasted for 24 h prior to the administration of the test compounds. The test compounds, **3a-j** were administered orally in doses up to 2000 mg/kg by suspending in 1% CMC solution and were kept under observation for period of 24 h.

Anti-inflammatory activity:

Carrageenan induced paw edema:

The anti-inflammatory activities¹⁴ of **3a-j** were assessed *in vitro* for their percent inhibition of paw edema in carrageenan model of inflammation in albino wistar rats using the method illustrated by Winter *et al.*¹⁵. After 16 h of fasting, the rats were divided into different groups of six each. Carrageenan (0.1 mL, 1%) was administered into the plantar surface of the right hind paw of the animals. The experimental groups, negative control group (1% CMC), and positive control group (10 mg/kg/po of diclofenac sodium) were given either the control drug and test compounds orally, 1 h prior to the administration of the carrageenan. Before injection of carrageenan, the average volume (V_0) of the right hind paw of each rat was calculated from 3 readings that did not deviate more than 3%. After injection of the phlogistic agent, the paw volume (V_t) was measured after 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th respectively with the aid of a digital plethysmometer. The edema was expressed as an increase in the volume of paw and percentage inhibition of acute edema was obtained as follows:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = [1 - (\Delta_v \text{ experimental} / \Delta_v \text{ control})] \times 100$$

where, $\Delta_v = V_t - V_0 = \text{Mean paw volume.}$

Results

1,3,5-Triphenyl-2-pyrazoline (3a): (Yield 95%, m.p. 185°C); IR (KBr), cm^{-1} : 3073, 3067, 3032, (aromatic C-H str), 2906 (aliphatic C-H str), 1492, 1500 (aromatic C=C), 1599 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ ppm: 3.11 (dd, 1H, (Ha), 3J 7.25 Hz, 2J 9.7 Hz), 3.81 (dd, 1H, (Hb), 3J 12.38 Hz, 2J 4.65 Hz), 5.24 (dd, 1H, (Hc), 3J 7.21 Hz, 2J 5.12 Hz), 6.77–7.77 (m, Ar-H, 15H). Mass (m/z): 298 (M^+), 300 ($M^+ + 1$).

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-1,5-diphenyl-2-pyrazoline (3b): (Yield 90%, m.p. 141°C); IR (KBr), cm^{-1} : 3088, 3037 (aromatic C-H str), 2935, 2906 (aliphatic C-H str), 1502, 1490 (aromatic C=C), 1597 (C=N), 748 (C-Cl); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3), δ , ppm: 3.08 (dd, 1H, (Ha), 3J 7.2 Hz, 2J 9.92 Hz), 3.80 (dd, 1H, (Hb), 3J 12.4 Hz, 2J 4.72 Hz), 5.20 (dd, 1H, (Hc), 3J 6.96 Hz, 2J 5.12 Hz), 6.78–7.94 (m, Ar-H, 14H). Mass (m/z): 334 ($M^+ + 2$).

3-(4-Bromophenyl)-1,5-diphenyl-2-pyrazoline (3c): (Yield 93%, m.p. 145°C); IR (KBr), cm^{-1} : 3078, 3023 (aromatic C-H str), 2936, 2907 (aliphatic C-H str), 1506, 1490 (aromatic C=C), 1598 (C=N), 698 (C-Br); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3), δ , ppm: 2.98 (dd, 1H (Ha), 3J 6.92 Hz, 2J 10.90 Hz), 3.89 (dd, 1H, (Hb), 3J 12.4 Hz, 2J 4.74 Hz), 5.62 (dd, 1H, (Hc), 3J 7.67 Hz, 2J 4.12 Hz), 6.79–7.59 (m, Ar-H, 14H). Mass (m/z): 376 ($M^+ - 1$).

5-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-1,3-diphenyl-2-pyrazoline (3d): (Yield 85%, m.p. 109°C); IR (KBr), cm^{-1} : 3077, 3021, 3001 (aromatic C-H str), 2953, 2933, (aliphatic C-H str), 1510, 1490 (aromatic C=C), 1598 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3), δ , ppm: 3.10 (dd, 1H, (Ha), 3J 7.72 Hz, 2J 9.36 Hz), 3.83 (dd, 1H, (Hb), 3J 12.39 Hz, 2J 4.67 Hz), 5.25 (dd, 1H, (Hc), 3J 7.68 Hz, 2J 4.6 Hz), 3.77 (m, 6H, -OCH₃), 6.31–7.83 (m, Ar-H, 13H). Mass (m/z): 360 ($M^+ + 1$).

3-(4-Bromophenyl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (3e): (Yield 63%, m.p. 215°C); IR (KBr), cm^{-1} : 3072, 3023 (aromatic C-H str), 2930, 2906 (aliphatic C-H str), 1501, 1487 (aromatic C=C), 1597 (C=N), 748 (C-Cl), 696 (C-Br); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3), δ , ppm: 3.26 (dd, 1H, (Ha), 3J 7.12 Hz, 2J 10.3 Hz), 3.75 (dd, 1H, (Hb), 3J 12.3 Hz, 2J 4.7 Hz), 5.68 (dd, 1H, (Hc), 3J 6.97 Hz, 2J 5.57 Hz), 7.25–7.68 (m, Ar-H, 13H). Mass (m/z): 412 ($M^+ + 1$).

3-(4-Bromophenyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (3f): (Yield 78%, m.p. 185°C); IR (KBr), cm^{-1} : 3077, 3051 (aromatic C-H str), 2918, 2894 (aliphatic C-H str), 1506, 1492 (aromatic C=C), 1597 (C=C), 1516 (asym) and 1335

(sym) (C-NO₂), 698 (C-Br); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ, ppm: 3.07 (dd, 1H, (Ha), ³J 7.18 Hz, ²J 9.90 Hz), 3.80 (dd, 1H, (Hb), ³J 12.4 Hz, ²J 4.64 Hz), 5.27 (dd, 1H, (Hc), ³J 6.96 Hz, ²J 5.21 Hz), 7.17–8.73 (m, Ar-H, 13H). Mass (*m/z*): 424 (M⁺ + 1).

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (3g): (Yield 83%, m.p. 205°C); IR (KBr), cm⁻¹: 3083, 3039, 3001 (aromatic C-H str), 2942, 2901 (aliphatic C-H str), 1500, 1489, (aromatic C...C), 1598 (C=N), 758, 747 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ, ppm: 3.01 (dd, 1H, (Ha), ³J 7.7 Hz, ²J 9.38 Hz), 3.53 (dd, 1H, (Hb), ³J 12.4 Hz, ²J 4.6 Hz), 5.27 (dd, 1H, (Hc), ³J 7.67 Hz, ²J 5.12 Hz), 6.79–7.87 (m, Ar-H, 13H). Mass (*m/z*): 367 (M⁺ + 1).

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (3h): (Yield 83%, m.p. 205°C); IR (KBr), cm⁻¹: 3080, 3051 (aromatic C-H str), 2942, 2901 (aliphatic C-H str), 2972, 2967 (-CH₃), 1501, 1490 (aromatic C...C), 1598 (C=N), 747 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ, ppm: 3.21 (dd, 1H, (Ha), ³J 7.72 Hz, ²J 9.98 Hz), 3.87 (dd, 1H, (Hb), ³J 12.44 Hz, ²J 4.56 Hz), 5.13 (dd, 1H, (Hc), ³J 7.2 Hz, ²J 4.9 Hz), 7.71–8.93 (m, Ar-H, 12H). Mass (*m/z*): 394.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (3i): (Yield 63%, m.p. 270°C); IR (KBr), cm⁻¹: 3089, 3047 (aromatic C-H str), 2935, 2906 (aliphatic C-H str), 1498, 1449 (aromatic C...C), 1596 (C=N), 1537 (asym) and 1350 (sym) (C-NO₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ, ppm: 2.91 (dd, 1H, (Ha), ³J 6.88 Hz, ²J 9.84 Hz), 3.81 (dd, 1H, (Hb), ³J 12.48 Hz, ²J 4.72 Hz), 5.31 (dd, 1H, (Hc), ³J 6.8 Hz, ²J 5.12 Hz), 7.19–7.43 (m, Ar-H, 13H). Mass (*m/z*): 378.

3-(4-Bromophenyl)-5-(4-bromophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (3j): (Yield 63%, m.p. 215°C); IR (KBr), cm⁻¹: 3077, 3063 (aromatic C-H str), 2987, 2916 (aliphatic C-H str), 1500, 1489 (aromatic C...C), 1597 (C=N), 698, 696 (C-Br); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ, ppm: 2.96 (dd, 1H, (Ha), ³J 6.84 Hz, ²J 10.36 Hz), 3.81 (dd, 1H, (Hb), ³J 12.4 Hz, ²J 4.62 Hz), 5.27 (dd, 1H, (Hc), ³J 6.8 Hz, ²J 5.64 Hz), 7.13–7.89 (m, Ar-H, 13H). Mass (*m/z*): 456.

Discussions

Antibacterial activity:

The antibacterial data indicated that the synthesized 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines (**3a-j**), showed significant antibacterial activity against Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus*, moderate activity against Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris* and weak activity against

Pseudomonas aeruginosa. It was to note that the compound (**3j**) carrying *p*-Br in two phenyl ring at C-3 and C-5 of pyrazoline moiety showed maximum activity followed by compound (**3e**) carrying *p*-Br and *p*-Cl in phenyl ring at C-3 and C-5 respectively against all the strains. It was interesting to note that the substitution of electron withdrawing group *p*-Cl in phenyl at C-3 and electron donating group *m,p*-OCH₃ in phenyl at C-5 led the compound (**3h**) found to be the good activity as compared to *m,p*-OCH₃ substitution only in compound (**3d**) against all strains. Detailed antimicrobial activities were tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical data of titled compounds

Comps.	x	y	% Yield	m.p (°C)	R _f
3a	H	H	83	183–185	0.79
3b	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	73	205–207	0.89
3c	<i>p</i> -Br	H	87	145–147	0.72
3d	H	<i>m,p</i> -OCH ₃	71	108–110	0.74
3e	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -Cl	73	115–117	0.42
3f	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	87	130–132	0.65
3g	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	77	200–204	0.73
3h	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m,p</i> -OCH ₃	60	110–112	0.66
3i	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	85	157–160	0.77
3j	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -Br	75	201–203	0.78

Anti-inflammatory activity:

Carrageenan-induced hind paw edema is the standard experimental model of acute inflammation. Carrageenan is the phlogistic agent of choice for testing anti-inflammatory drugs as it is not known to be antigenic and is devoid of apparent systemic effects. The carrageenan test was selected because of its sensitivity in detecting orally active anti-inflammatory agents particularly in the acute phase of inflammation. The percent inhibition of edema was calculated against the control on the basis of experimental data obtained.

The percent inhibition was calculated from 1st hour to 5th h as carrageenan-induced edema is a biphasic response. The first phase (0–3 h after injection of carrageenan) is mediated through the release of histamine, serotonin and kinins where as, the second phase is related to the release of prostaglandins and bradykinins.

All the 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline derivatives exhibited encouraging anti-inflammatory activity. The oral administration of different derivatives of 2-pyrazoline suppresses

inflammation during both the phase. The compounds showed ranging from 50.95% to 63.59% and 57.80% to 83.67% where as standard drug diclofenac showed 70.35% and 87.17% inhibition after 3rd and 5th h respectively. Detailed anti-inflammatory activities are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines

Compds.	Zone of inhibition (in mm)			
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
3a	15	-	8	6
3b	14	10	7	8
3c	17	16	11	7
3d	12	11	7	8
3e	21	18	17	12
3f	18	14	15	10
3g	20	15	11	12
3h	15	17	15	11
3i	18	14	15	10
3j	23	21	21	13
Tetracycline	27	25	23	18
DMSO	-	-	-	-
Control				

Table 3. Anti-inflammatory activity of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolines

Compound	% inhibition \pm SEM	
	3 h	5 h
Standard	71.35 \pm 3.55***	88.16 \pm 1.77***
Control	-	-
3a	50.92 \pm 1.559*	57.82 \pm 3.007*
3b	54.93 \pm 1.967*	63.80 \pm 1.217*
3c	54.95 \pm 1.51*	62.83 \pm 3.21*
3d	66.59 \pm 1.344**	78.01 \pm 1.660**
3e	61.75 \pm 1.376*	74.64 \pm 1.374**
3f	63.59 \pm 1.644**	75.01 \pm 0.470**
3g	61.57 \pm 1.631**	69.71 \pm 0.673**
3h	68.75 \pm 1.376*	83.67 \pm 1.574***
3i	65.95 \pm 1.159*	73.80 \pm 2.007*
3j	63.59 \pm 1.641**	70.71 \pm 0.673**

Percentage inhibition are expressed in mean \pm SEM (n = 6 for each compound).

Statistical analysis:

The data were analyzed by One-Way ANOVA, at 99% confidence interval, followed by Dunnett's Multiple Comparison Test as post hoc analysis. * p < 0.05 Significant Difference, ** p < 0.01 Significant, *** p < 0.001 Highly Significant compared to control and student t-test.

The anti-inflammatory activities data showed that compound (**3h**) having *m,p*-OCH₃ and *p*-Cl groups in the phenyl ring at C-5 and C-3 respectively of pyrazoline nucleus poses highest activity followed by compound (**3d**) having *m,p*-OCH₃ group in the phenyl ring at C-5. It was noted in compounds (**3b**) and (**3c**) that the *para* substitution of electron withdrawing groups of phenyl ring attached to C-3 in pyrazoline moiety shown lesser percentage of anti-inflammatory activity. It was interesting to note that when both the phenyl rings at C-3 and C-5 substituted with electron withdrawing groups showed significant anti-inflammatory activity. The low toxicity of synthesized compounds was evident from the observation that there was no mortality in rat at doses up to 2000 mg/kg.

Conclusion

The present study focused on potentially active skeleton of 2-pyrazolines. The antibacterial activity of different derivatives of 3,5-diaryl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline was investigated by means of cup plate method. It was found that electron withdrawing groups (*p*-Br and/or *p*-Cl) attached to the phenyl ring at C-3 and C-5 of pyrazoline nucleus showed promising antibacterial activity and it was observed that the compounds **3j** and **3e** showed highest inhibitory activity against all strains of bacteria. The exact mechanism of action of antibacterial was not performed yet. The oral administration of different derivatives of 2-pyrazoline suppresses inflammation during both the phase and mechanism of action probably or might be linked to lipoxygenase and/or cyclooxygenase. The presence of electron donating group *m,p*-OCH₃ at C-5 and electron withdrawing group *p*-Cl at C-3 of phenyl ring of compound **3h** showed maximum inhibitory response as compared to other derivatives and very nearer to standard drug diclofenac. The synthesized compounds had shown good anti-inflammatory and found to be good inhibitor of pain. It was interesting to know that the compound **3h** which was found to be good anti-inflammatory agent, which was comparable with the standard drug diclofenac. These synthesized drugs can be extended for further detailed study.

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